

Disposable uric acid biosensor by bacterial crude uricase enzyme modified screen printed electrode

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Abstract : Uric acid is the primary end product from purine derivatives in human metabolism. Excessive production of uric acid may lead to gout, hyperuricemia and kidney disorder. Different analytical methods for uric acid such as colorimetry, commercial enzyme electrode and commercially available uric acid kit are used widely. The main purpose of this research was to develop a screen printed electrode based uric acid biosensor using gelatin immobilized uricase enzyme extracted from *Comamonas* sp. BTUA. The enzyme catalyzed oxidation of uric acid in presence of oxygen, producing allantoin and hydrogen peroxide. The linearity of the standard curve in the concentration ranges from 5.94×10^{-6} to 4.75×10^{-4} molar was satisfactory and could be used for the quantitative determination of uric acid in human serum samples. The limit of detection (LOD) was 2.26 μM and sensitivity was evaluated as 3.31 nA μM^{-1} of uric acid. One modified electrode could be used for six measurements with 95% accuracy up to 25 days. The developed biosensor was easy to use, inexpensive, sensitive and reliable.

Keywords : Uric acid, gout, *Comamonas* sp., uricase, amperometry, screen printed electrode.

Introduction

Uric acid is produced as the end product during purine metabolism in human. Uric acid is present in human and other higher primates as an antioxidant. The normal range of uric acid in human serum is 2–8 mg/dL (approx. 118–475 μM). Excessive serum uric acid leads to gout, hyperuricemia and kidney disorder. Monitoring uric acid level in blood and urine is essential for diagnosis of the above diseases. Different uric acid estimation methods are reported in literature such as spectrophotometry, fluorimetry, electrochemical, chemiluminescence¹, fluorescent sol-gel method², enzyme electrode^{3,4} and commercial uric acid kits⁵ are available. Among all these methods electrochemical procedure is most sensitive and reliable. Different biosensing procedures have been developed by immobilizing uricase with conducting polymers^{6,7}, nanoelectrodes^{8,9} and metal oxide nano flakes¹⁰ on electrode surface. Many disposable screen printed electrode systems have also been reported in literature. Zen *et al.* (2002) used an enzyme-less sensing system for uric acid deter-

mination based on nontronite-coated screen printed electrode¹¹. Piermarini *et al.* (2013) used electrochemically deposited prussian blue on screen printed electrode for uric acid determination¹². The use of screen printed electrode (SPE) for biosensor development has been very beneficial due to its disposable nature and low cost. In recent days SPE was used in biosensing systems such as prussian blue modified platinum, gold SPE for biosensor application for hydrogen peroxide detection^{13,14}, nafion coated SPE for cholinesterase detection¹⁵. Other SPE based biosensors where working electrode was modified with different enzymes such as acetylcholinesterase¹⁶ for organophosphates, pyruvate oxidase in phosphate biosensor¹⁷. Enzymes were entrapped or immobilized within membrane or films such as glucose oxidase entrapped in nafion film on carbon-SPE¹⁸, diamine oxidase entrapped in poly (HEMA) film¹⁹ for better result. Enzyme ink was also used for rapid and sensitive detection²⁰.

In present study, gelatin was used for immobilization of uricase on rhodinated carbon ink screen printed elec-

trode. Gelatin is a collagen derivative and a heterogeneous mixture of single or multi stranded polypeptides. Gelatin possesses a polyampholytic property. This is due to the presence of both positively charged (arginine, lysine, histidine) and negatively charged (glutamic acid and aspartic acid) amino acids²¹. Gelatin also exhibits a unique amino acid sequence such as glycine, proline and 4-hydroxyproline which is suitable for hydrogel formation upon cross linking. A typical structure of gelatin is – Ala-Gly-Pro-Arg-Gly-Glu-4Hyp-Gly-Pro-²². Gelatin can be crosslinked with glyoxal, epoxides, isocyanates, formaldehydes, glutaraldehyde etc. Glutaraldehyde is the most widely accepted immobilizer for its efficiency as collagenous materials stabilizer²³. It is easily available and inexpensive. At a temperature around 40 °C gelatin aqueous solutions are in sol state and thermo-reversible gelling is possible on cooling at 37 °C. Conformational transition and partial recovery of collagen triple-helix structure occurred upon cooling process. Gelatin film provides a smooth surface with free amino groups which can cross-link with C=O group. In this process, glutaraldehyde crosslinks the free amino groups of lysine or hydroxylysine on gelatin during gel formation. At neutral to slightly alkaline pH, cross-linking is favoured by nucleophilic addition [ϵ -NH₂ groups to the carbonyl groups (C=O) of aldehyde] and protonation of -OH yields the conjugated Schiff bases²⁴.

Results and discussion

Characterization of SPE/Gel/GLA/Urc :

SEM images of modified and unmodified SPE working electrode was studied for surface morphology. The rhodinated carbon paste working electrode surface (Fig. 1A) was examined before and after enzyme immobilization. The WE was observed with irregular deposition of carbon flakes without any surface deposition (Fig. 1B). The flake surface was smooth before uricase cross-linking on working electrode. Uricase immobilization on the working electrode surface was visualized as granular structure. Carbon flakes were observed with aggregated uricase cross-linked to gelatin thin film (Fig. 1C and D).

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of SPE. (A) Magnified image of SPE showing working electrode (WE); (B) and (C) Working electrode surface of SPE before and after uricase immobilization; (D) Magnified image of cross-linked enzyme aggregate on modified SPE (Gel/GLA/Urc).

Influence of pH and scan rates on oxidation peak potential and peak current of uric acid during cyclic voltammetry :

The oxidation of uric acid on the uricase modified SPE was specifically obtained at -0.184 V by cyclic voltammetry (CV). The CV was executed in the potential range of -1.5 V to $+1.5$ V with a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ (Fig. 2). The highest response current was generated at pH 8.5 of 0.1 M SB with respect to other buffered pH (Fig. 3A). Protonation (pH < 7) and over deprotonation (pH > 8.5) of modified SPE resulted into much lowering in uricase activity. Thus a pH of 8.5 was maintained in all experiments. Variation of scan rate (10 – 100 mV s⁻¹) was studied for monitoring reaction kinetics. The peak current (i_p) increased proportionally with increased scan rates (Fig. 3B). The i_p was plotted against square root of scan rates with a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.99$. This predicted that a diffusion control system prevailed for the modified electrode. A shift was observed in peak potential (E_p) from -0.184 V to 0.202 V. Shift in E_p depicted an irreversible oxidation of uric acid on modified SPE surface.

Measurement of uric acid concentration :

Uric acid standard solutions were measured by chronoamperometry at fixed potential (-0.184 V). The biosensor showed linear range (Fig. 4) from 5.94 μ M to

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram showing oxidation potential of uric acid at -0.184 V . Peak current increases with increasing uric acid concentration at fixed potential.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH and scan rates on response current. (A) Effect of pH on response current with $50\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ uric acid in working buffer ($0.1\text{ M SB} + 0.1\text{ M KCl}$). (B) Effect of scan rates on the pattern of cyclic voltammogram (forward scan only) showing increase in peak current with increasing scan rates.

$475\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ with standard equation $Y = 3.313x + 19.361$ ($R^2 = 0.98$). The sensitivity was calculated as $3.31\text{ nA }\mu\text{M}^{-1}$ (slope of the standard equation) with a detection limit $2.26\text{ }\mu\text{M}$. The response time was found to be 12 s after addition of uric acid. Thus SPE/Gel/GLA/Urc biosensor was very sensitive to uric acid. The system was tested using pure enzyme (Sigma) and the results were very much comparable.

Real sample analysis :

Five human serum samples were collected from local

diagnostic clinic and uric acid was measured by using biosensor. Quantitative measurements were analysed and compared with clinical report. The uric acid values (spiked sample) obtained with biosensor were found to vary in the range of $126\text{--}148\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ with a RSD% ($n = 5$) 0.7 to 1.4 (Table 1). Real sample analysis results were quite satisfactory and hence the system could be used for analysis in clinical laboratory.

Storage stability :

The storage stability of SPE/Gel/GLA/Urc was car-

Fig. 4. Standard curve of uric acid at a concentration range 29.7–356.4 μM . Inset : Linear ranges of uric acid at lower concentration ranges from 5.94 to 29.7 μM .

Table 1. Real sample analysis study using SPE/Gel/GLA/Urc biosensor. Samples were diluted in working buffer (0.1 M SB + 0.1 M KCl). Results representing the mean \pm SD of four consecutive experiments for each samples

Blood serum samples	Clinical report (μ mole/L)	Spike (μM)	Expected (μM)	Found (μM)	Recovery (%)	RSD ($n = 5$) (%)
I	137	10	147	144.9 \pm 1.08	98.57	0.748
II	116	20	136	136.4 \pm 0.95	100.29	0.701
III	115	10	125	126.24 \pm 1.73	100.99	1.374
IV	125	20	145	146.16 \pm 1.53	100.80	1.053
V	140	10	150	148.36 \pm 2.11	98.91	1.428

Table 2. Study on storage stability. Response was measured after 5 days intervals

Time (Days)	1	5	10	15	20	25	30
Relative response (%)	100	99.1	98.2	96.4	96.0	95.5	82.0

ried out by analyzing 50 μM standard solution of uric acid for 5 days intervals after preparation of the modified electrode. 95% of initial response was retained even after 25 days of electrode preparation. After 30 days a lowering (82%) in response was detected.

Experimental

Reagents :

Crude uricase was extracted from an isolated bacterium, *Comamonas* sp. BTUA (NCBI Gen Bank Acc No. GU265556), pure uricase (EC1.7.3.3) was supplied by Sigma (UK). Horseradish peroxidase (EC1.11.1.7) were purchased from Sigma (UK) and uric acid, boric acid,

Fig. 5. Schematic of screen printed electrode (SPE) [Numerical representing the actual dimensions in mm]; Inset : Original photograph of SPE.

borax, phenol, 4-aminoantipyrine (4-AAP), sodium chloride, gelatin Type A (Gel), glutaraldehyde (GLA) and

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of enzyme immobilization on SPE-working electrode.

other chemicals were supplied by Himedia, India. 18.2 M Ω Milli-Q (Millipore, India) water was used for preparing buffers and reagent solutions. All experiments were conducted at room temperature (27 $^{\circ}$ C).

Instrument :

Cyclic voltammograms (CV) and chronoamperometry were performed using AUTOLAB, PGSTAT 12 (Ecochemie B.V., The Netherlands). A screen printed electrode (SPE) system – a working (rhodinised carbon) electrode, a carbon counter electrode and an Ag-AgCl paste reference electrode was used as transducers. The respective terminals of SPE were connected via standard connector to data acquisition and experimental control software (GPES software; version 4.9). Surface morphology of modified electrode was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Quanta 200, USA).

Screen printed electrode (SPE) fabrication :

SPEs were printed onto a polyester sheet (Cadillac Plastic Ltd., Swindon, UK) using a DEK 248 screen-printing machine (DEK Printing Machines Ltd., Waymouth, UK). The working electrode was fabricated from a commercially available carbon powder (MCA Services Ltd., Cambs., UK). The carbon powder was made into a screen-printable paste by mixing 1 : 3 (w/w) with 2.5% w/v hydroxy ethyl cellulose (HEC) in PBS. The 15% w/w silver chloride in silver paste (MCA) was used to prepare reference electrode. The counter electrode and basal tracks were fabricated from 145Rcarbon ink (MCA) to connect the electrodes to the measurement device. The insulation was prepared by using an epoxy-based protective coating ink 242-SB (Agmet ESL Ltd.,

Reading, UK). The electrodes were then heat treated at 125 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 h to cure the epoxy resin and to stabilize the electrocatalytic pad to allow prolonged use of the device in aqueous solutions^{25,26}.

Immobilization of uricase :

Uricase was immobilized on circular electrocatalytic working electrode using 20% gelatin (Gel). At first, a thin film of gel was prepared first onto the electrode surface and allowed to cross-link in presence of 2% glutaraldehyde (GLA) for 1 h. The cross-linked film (Gel/GLA) was then allowed to dry at room temperature. The fully dried film was then dipped in the uricase solution (0.1 U/ml) for 1 h. The uricase immobilized SPE (Gel/GLA/Urc) was washed thoroughly with buffer to remove unbound enzyme and stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C until use. In this immobilization phenomenon, the gel thin film provided activated amine groups ($-\text{NH}_2^+$) exposed on the surface. Upon cross-linking, the surface became covered with aldehyde ($-\text{CHO}$) groups of GLA as shown in Fig. 2. The GLA on the other hand, provided enough binding sites for uricase on the cross-linked gelatin surface via free- NH_2^+ groups on enzyme.

Preparation of standard solutions :

A 2 mM stock solution of uric acid was prepared in 0.1 M sodium borate buffer (SB), pH 8.5. Uric acid standard solutions (5–500 μ M) were prepared from stock using 0.1 M SB and 0.1 M KCl.

Determination of uric acid :

Uric acid was determined following the generic cata-

lytic reaction mediated by uricase :

Oxidation potential of uric acid on modified (SPE/Gel/GLA/Urc) electrode was determined by CV with various uric acid concentrations. CV was performed at a wide range i.e. -1.5 V to $+1.5$ V at different proton concentrations (pH 5.5 to 11) and at various scan rates (10 – 100 mV s^{-1}) to optimize the response for 50 μM uric acid standard solution. The current generated due to oxidation of uric acid was polarized at -0.184 V (determined from cyclic voltammogram vs Ag/AgCl paste reference electrode on SPE). The response current was directly proportional to uric acid concentration in this modified system. Prior to actual measurements, the modified SPE was equilibrated with 50 μL of working buffer (0.1 M SB, pH 8.5 + 0.1 M KCl) for 5 min. The activated SPE was then connected to AUTOLAB potentiostat/galvanostat by standard connector. The chronoamperometry was performed at fixed potential (-0.184 V) for standard uric acid solutions with time. The response current with working buffer (without uric acid) was measured as baseline and was subtracted from every measurement generated by uric acid standard solutions. The total reaction volume used was 200 μL for all the measurements.

Conclusion

An amperometric disposable biosensor was developed by immobilizing crude uricase in gelatin thin film on rhodinated carbon screen printed electrode. The enzyme electrode was found very sensitive towards uric acid at micromolar level with a detection limit of 2.26 μM . The sensitivity of the sensor was much higher i.e. 3.31 $\text{nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$ than that reported in literature and this provided the sensor greater usability even at lower ranges. The response was found to be linear at wide range (5.94 – 475 μM) which included the normal serum uric acid range in human. The sensor could be used for six consecutive measurements up to 25 days of electrode preparation. The most interesting finding of this research work was that the crude enzyme derived from a microbe could be used at nominal cost and the results compared very well

with that of pure enzyme.

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References

1. H. Chu, X. Wei, M. Wu, J. Yan and Y. Tu, *Sensors and Actuators (B)*, 2012, **163**, 247.
2. D. Martinez-Pérez, M. L. Ferer and C. R. Mateo, *Anal. Biochem.*, 2003, **322**, 238.
3. E. Akyilmaz, M. K. Sezgentürk and E. Dinckaya, *Talanta*, 2003, **61**, 73.
4. F. Zhang, X. Wang, S. Ai, Z. Sun, Q. Wan, Z. Zhu, Y. Xian, L. Jin and K. Yamamoto, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 2004, **519**, 155.
5. BioAssay Systems, QuantiChrom™ Uric Acid Assay Kit (DIUA-250) 2007. [Internet]. <http://www.medibena.at/media/BAS/product-sheets/diua.pdf> (Accessed January 2010).
6. K. Arora, G. Sumana, V. Saxena, R. K. Gupta, S. K. Gupta, J. V. Yakhmi, M. K. Pandey, S. Chand and B. D. Malhotra, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 2007, **594**, 17.
7. F. Arslan, *Sensors*, 2008, **8**, 5492.
8. G. Yang, L. Tan, Y. Shi, S. Wang, X. Lu, H. Bai and Y. Yang, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **30**, 454.
9. F. Zhiang, X. Wang, S. Ai, Z. Sun, Q. Wan, Z. Zhu, Y. Xian, L. Jin and K. Yamamoto, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 2004, **519**, 155.
10. S. M. U. Ali, Z. H. Ibutoto, M. Kashif, U. Hashim and M. Willander, *Sensors*, 2012, **12**, 2787.
11. M. J. Zen, Y. Y. Lai, H. H. Yang and A. Senthil Kumar, *Sensors and Actuator (B)*, 2002, **84**, 237.
12. S. Piermarinia, D. Migliorelli, G. V. Renato, M. A. Pierantozzib, C. Corteseb and G. Palleschi, *Sensors and Actuators (B)*, 2013, **179**, 170.
13. M. P. O'Halloran, M. Pravda and G. G. Guilbault, *Talanta*, 2001, **55**, 605.
14. I. Luiz de Mattos, L. Gorton and T. Ruzgas, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 2003, **18**, 193.
15. A. Veseli, A. Hajrizi, T. Arbneshi and K. Kalcher, *J. Electrochem. Sci. Eng.*, 2012, **2**, 199.
16. E. V. Gogol, G. A. Evtugyn, J. L. Marty, H. C. Budnikov and V. G. Winter, *Talanta*, 2000, **53**, 379.
17. A. Crewa, D. Lonsdaleb, N. Byrdc, R. Pittsond and J. P. Harta, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 2011, **26**, 2847.
18. L. Gilberta, A. T. A. Jenkinsb, S. Browning and J. P. Harta, *Sensors and Actuators (B)*, 2011, **160**, 1322.
19. C. M. Keow, F. Abu Bakar, S. Abu Bakar, L. Y.

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- Heng, R. Wagiran and S. Siddiquee, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2012, **7**, 4702.
20. P. Chen, Y. Peng, M. He, X. C. Yan, Y. Zhang and Y. N. Liu, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2013, **8**, 8931.
21. A. Bigi, G. Cojazzi, S. Panzavolta, K. Rubini and N. Rovey, *Biomaterials*, 2001, **22**, 763.
22. Y. M. Lim, H. J. Gwon, J. H. Choi, J. Shin and Y. C. Nho, *Macromolecular Research*, 2010, **18**, 29.
23. L. J. Yang and Y. C. Ou, *Lab Chip.*, 2005, **5**, 979.
24. S. Farris, J. Song and Q. Huang, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2010, **58**, 998.
25. D. Bhattacharyay, K. Dutta, S. Banerjee, A. P. F. Turner and P. Sarkar, *Electroanalysis*, 2008, **20**, 1947.
26. P. Pal, P. Sarkar, D. Bhattacharyay and S. Pal, *Sensor Lett.*, 2010, **8**, 577.

